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ACTION

OPEN DATA PORTAL

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Abstract	This deliverable describes the updates introduced in the second version of Data Portal. It is based on Zenodo and the research objects identified in the catalogue have been integrated in the portal
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TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
1 INTRODUCTION	4
2. Updates on ACTION Open Data Portal	6
2.1 Platform updates	7
2.2 Results updates	9
3 CONCLUSIONS	9

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of the objectives of ACTION is to “*create a digital infrastructure to help citizen scientists easily set up and manage projects in all their online and offline manifestations, manage and share their data openly, and comply with RRI (Responsible Research and Innovation) practises*”. In this context, ACTION will provide to the projects (pilots) a repository to publish their data.

The objective of this deliverable/document is to describe the updates introduced in the new version of the data portal. These are related with the addition of new resources and with the integration of the research objects published in our catalogue..

Our data portal is not only a repository of data, where all users upload datasets, it is a repository for all project’s outputs that can be used for researching. Our approach, following the one described in the previous version of this deliverable, is based on Zenodo, a repository to deposit research resources developed by OpenAire.

New pilots in ACTION have received training to publish their data in Zenodo and link their research outputs to our Open Data Portal. The resources of ACTION amount to **35321 views** and **3823 downloads**.

The platform is aligned with the work done on the Research Object Catalogue, where a collection of research objects have been created for each pilot to model the work done. These collections were built using a tool called ASSET, deployed by ACTION, which generates files that are compatible with our portal, facilitating its integration.

The data portal is available here: <https://data.actionproject.eu/>

1 INTRODUCTION

The objective of this deliverable is to describe the updates of the ACTION open data portal which allows citizens to access the outcomes generated in ACTION and all of their pilots.

According to the European Commission¹, an Open Data Portal (ODP) is a *web-based interface designed to make it easier to find re-usable information*. To make the information re-usable, it must be published with proper licences and with a set of appropriate metadata.

The previous version of this deliverable described the decisions taken with regards to the initial design and deployment of an open data portal. The chosen repository for the gathered data was Zenodo², on which an ElasticSearch database was built to bypass the restrictions imposed by Zenodo and its API.

Figure 1 depicts this architecture.

Fig 1. Open Data Portal Architecture

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/open-data-portals>

² <https://zenodo.org/>

OPEN DATA PORTAL

On ElasticSearch, a minimal frontend based on HTML and Javascript was deployed. This web interface allows users to search, among the outcomes of the project uploaded to Zenodo, resources filtered by categories, title, description and projects.

Our platform supports multiple communities and, as of this moment, a software module periodically updates the ElasticSearch with the new resources deposited in all our three communities in Zenodo.

New features have been introduced in this new version, in particular, the integration of the research objects. Figure 2 depicts the current process to index resources in our platform.

Figure 2. Process to update data and architecture overview

A research object is an aggregation of digital objects that represent a research. In the context of ACTION, a collection of research objects have been created to represent the knowledge of each pilot (see D4.7 Research Object Catalogue). These objects have been created with a customization of the tool ASSET. Results are modelled following the specification RO-Crate and integrated in the Open Data Portal

2. Updates on the ACTION Open Data Portal

The open data portal has been updated with the results generated by the project in this last year, including the outcomes of the six new pilots that joined in the second open call. Also, the platform has been updated with the integration of Research Objects.

2.1 Platform updates

The platform has been updated to integrate the results generated in the Research Object Catalogue (see D4.7 Research Object Catalogue v2). A research object is an aggregation of research outputs (publications, data, software, etc.). These research objects contain information that is not present in our Zenodo community and can be relevant for researchers, such as GitHub repositories, websites with tutorials or guidelines, audios in other repositories, etc .

Our main objective, in this version, was to integrate both products. This was achieved using a metadata-description file of the research objects which was created using the aforementioned tool ASSET (<https://ro.actionproject.eu/>), adapted to the ACTION project’s needs.

This tool, shown in Figure 3, allows users to model their research objects, including metadata from their outputs and the relation between them.

Fig 3. ASSET tool interface

ASSET has a collection of different digital objects that can be included in the research object to simplify the process to the users and to use a common vocabulary. Each research object created, also referred here as resource, is defined into one of these categories:

- Database
- Data

OPEN DATA PORTAL

- Software
- Presentations
- Publications
- Webpages
- Visualisations
- Video
- Image
- Audio

Note that these resources are not only files uploaded to Zenodo, any resource available in the WWW can be added. The research objects database section contains the list of all the resources available in Zenodo. This facilitates the addition of new resources in the diagram because the metadata of the digital objects are added automatically based on the metadata present in Zenodo.

With this tool, users can generate a JSON file based on RO-Crate that can be interpreted by our open data portal to display the results of a project. Figure 4 shows the presentation of these results in the Open Data Portal.

The screenshot shows a web page titled "Resources" with a light blue background. The page is organized into five main sections, each with a dark blue header bar:

- DATASETS**: Contains "Noise Maps ACTION pilot data 2020" with a description of the noise maps project in Barcelona and a CC-BY-4.0 license.
- AUDIO**: Contains "Raval May2020" with a description of ambient urban audio from Raval and a "Not Specified" license.
- SOFTWARE**: Contains "AudioMoth-Firmware-SPL" (describing an adaptation of AudioMoth firmware for SPL calculation) and "Training corpus" (describing sounds used for training). Licenses are MIT License and Private, respectively.
- PRESENTATIONS**: Contains "Data visualization with Grafana" with a description of presentations for ACTION pilots and a CC-BY-4.0 license.
- ADDITIONAL INFORMATION**: Contains "Noise Maps Dashboards" with a description of Grafana dashboards and a "Not Specified" license.

Fig 4. Research object results

The results shown in figure 4 are grouped respecting the categories defined in the research object catalogue and listed in the previous section. All resources can be clicked if a public uri was added to the definition of the research object.

In this GitHub repository³, can be found in the files generated using this tool for ACTION.

2.2 Results updates

The platform has been fed with the new results generated in the project. It includes the new deliverables and guidelines, and the results of the new pilots incorporated last year. Also, the new resources identified in the Research Object Catalogue have been aggregated. Some related diagrams are visible in the examples section of the ASSET tool.

At the time of presenting this deliverable, the numbers of the portal are the following:

- Number of deliverables: 36
- Number of articles: 9
- Number of posters: 12
- Number of presentations: 10
- Number of images: 1
- Number of pieces of software: 24
- Number of Research Data: 24

Our resources in the Open Data Portal amount to a total of **35321 views** and **3823 downloads**.

³ https://github.com/actionprojecteu/research_objects_catalogue

3 CONCLUSIONS

We have maintained the structure of the platform based on Zenodo, where the projects and the pilots have deposited their research outputs. The approach described in this deliverable improves the sustainability of the portal, relying on the OpenAire infrastructure. Resources are automatically indexed in the portal everytime a resource is incorporated in our community in Zenodo, and thus immediately findable.

The portal was also successfully aligned with our Research Object Catalogue, so that every time that a research object is updated, changes are propagated to our Data Portal.

Finally, The adaptation of the ASSET tool is correctly working, allowing citizens to easily edit their Research Objects.